

Temperature-Dependent Elastic and Inelastic Thermal Neutron Scattering in MgO using Machine-Learned Force Fields

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ABSTRACT

Coherent elastic neutron scattering is characterized by Bragg energies and their corresponding structure factors, which together can describe the relationship between thermal neutrons and the periodic structure of the material. Material temperature can affect both (1) the contribution of a given Bragg condition to the coherent elastic scattering cross section, and (2) the Bragg energy values due to thermal expansion of the lattice. The Evaluated Nuclear Data Format (ENDF-6) does not support the specification of temperature-dependent Bragg edge energies in File 7. Consequently, Bragg edge energies are only provided at one temperature (typically room temperature) and assumed to be temperature invariant. With the adoption of the Generalized Nuclear Data Structure (GNDS) format, however, use of fully temperature-dependent coherent elastic scattering models is now possible. The purpose of this paper is to create an example thermal scattering law evaluation to inform improvements that will be needed to nuclear data processing and neutron transport application codes to support the relaxation of this physics approximation in ENDF/B-IX. Magnesium oxide (MgO) is used as the example material because it has a cubic structure and lattice parameter measurements spanning a wide range of temperatures. A fully temperature-dependent scattering model is developed using a machine-learned potential (MLP) which is then compared to a partially temperature-dependent model developed using standard assumptions for solid moderators. These comparisons emphasize the impact of temperature on Bragg energies.

Keywords: Thermal Neutron Scattering, MgO, temperature-dependent, MLP, ENDF

1. INTRODUCTION

Thermal neutron scattering law (TSL) evaluations available in the ENDF/B-VIII.1 library [1] were predominantly developed from materials models that neglect full temperature effects from atomic vibrations (e.g., phonons) and crystalline structure, which influence inelastic and elastic scattering, respectively. However, a prior criticality study of TRIGA and SNAP-10A reactor models demonstrated that temperature-dependent material models can influence estimates of criticality and reactivity feedback effects at elevated temperature [2]. The use of temperature-independent material models for inelastic scattering is a simplifying approximation that has historically been used in solid moderators due to limitations in computational materials modeling methods, but for elastic scattering it is also a structural limitation of the ENDF-6 format [3].

High-fidelity TSL evaluations can be derived from atomistic simulations, which require force fields that accurately capture the quantum mechanical force field of the real material. Modern solid moderator and reflector TSL evaluations are largely developed from *ab initio* lattice dynamics (AILD) [4, 5] – a predictive, computationally light-weight technique. In AILD the phonon spectrum (a material input to TSL generation) is computed from a quantum mechanical force field but assumes harmonic interatomic forces, thereby excluding the anharmonicity that drives temperature-dependent softening of the

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phonon spectrum as well as spectral broadening (i.e., smearing of phonon spectrum features). *Ab initio* molecular dynamics (AIMD) [6, 7] was intended to introduce anharmonicity to accurately generate phonon spectra for a wide range of temperatures, but it is prohibitively computationally expensive.

Machine-learned force fields, also known as machine-learned interatomic potentials (MLPs), have been introduced to established TSL generation workflows to overcome the deficiencies of AILD and AIMD [8]. MLPs are trained to accurately represent computed quantum mechanical force fields so as to accurately predict a wide range of material properties including phonons [9]. MLPs can be used efficiently in molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, which inherently include temperature-dependent phonon effects from anharmonicity. Phonons generated with an YH_x MLP have been shown to accurately reproduce inelastic neutron scattering measurements from 5–800 K [8]; however, hydrogen diffusion that cannot be incorporated into existing solid moderator TSL models was observed above 800 K [8].

In this work, a TSL for magnesium oxide (MgO) is developed using inelastic and elastic data, derived from an MLP that is trained on a variety of MgO structures. MgO is an inorganic compound with a cubic rock-salt structure and has lattice parameter measurements spanning a wide range of temperatures. It is used as a moderator in conceptual small high-temperature gas reactors [10] and consists of a single phase up to 3100 K [11] while not exhibiting significant diffusion effects, as is observed in metal hydrides, making it an ideal test case for examining TSL generation with MLP-based phonons.

2. BACKGROUND

Thermal neutron scattering events can be classified as either coherent or incoherent, depending on the presence or absence of neutron wave interference, and as either elastic or inelastic, which, in solids, is dependent on whether neutrons interact with the vibrational modes of a material. Often times, the coherent effects present in inelastic scattering are neglected, resulting in all inelastic scattering being treated as if it were incoherent. Thus, the types of thermal scattering typically considered are inelastic, coherent elastic, and incoherent elastic.

2.1. Inelastic

Inelastic thermal neutron scattering in solids is characterized by neutrons exciting and/or de-exciting vibrational modes (i.e., phonons) in the material. Such scattering events contribute to the thermal neutron scattering law $S(\alpha, \beta, T)$, which is a relation between the unitless momentum exchange parameter α , unitless energy exchange parameter β , and material temperature T . The scattering law can be used to calculate the double-differential scattering cross section $\sigma(E \rightarrow E', \mu, T)$ where E is the initial neutron energy, E' is the final neutron energy, and μ is the cosine of the scattering angle.

To describe the neutron-phonon interactions that characterize inelastic thermal neutron scattering, two key properties must be known: (1) the available phonon modes in the material, and (2) the phonon modes that are excited within the material. The first property is represented by the material's phonon density of states (DOS), also known as the phonon distribution, while the second is described by phonon occupation statistics. While both properties exhibit temperature dependence, the temperature dependence of the first property is often neglected for solid materials. Regardless as to whether a material's phonon distribution is considered temperature dependent, there will always be *some* temperature dependence accounted for in the occupation statistics. This is represented in Fig. 1.

2.2. Elastic Scattering

Elastic thermal scattering in solids occurs without interaction with phonon modes, meaning neutrons exit with the same energy E as they had upon arrival. Elastic scattering is classified as coherent or incoherent, depending on the bound scattering cross section of the target nuclide and the structure of the material. Coherent scattering patterns emerge when the material is sufficiently well-ordered. Inco-

Figure 1. Workflow for processing inelastic thermal neutron scattering data when prepared using a temperature-independent phonon distribution (A) and a set of temperature-dependent phonon distributions (B).

herent scattering results from disorder in the material and from incoherent neutron-nucleus scattering events.

Both elastic scattering processes are described using the Debye-Waller coefficient, which is a function of the mean square displacement of the nucleus from its equilibrium site. The Debye-Waller coefficient can be defined as

$$W(T) = \frac{1}{Ak_B T} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\rho(\beta, T)}{2\beta \sinh\left(\frac{\beta}{2}\right)} \times e^{\frac{\beta}{2}} d\beta \quad (1)$$

where $\rho(\beta, T)$ is the phonon distribution, A is the atomic weight ratio, and k_B is the Boltzmann constant. Note that the Debye-Waller coefficient is temperature dependent both explicitly in its formulation and due to its dependence on the phonon distribution. Even if the phonon distribution is approximated as temperature independent, there remains some temperature dependence in the derived quantity.

The Debye-Waller coefficient is used in defining both the incoherent elastic scattering cross section,

$$\sigma_{\text{inc,el}}(E) = \frac{\sigma_{\text{b,inc}}}{4W(T)E} \times \left(1 - e^{-4W(T)E}\right) \quad (2)$$

as well as the coherent elastic scattering cross section,

$$\sigma_{\text{coh,el}}(E) = \frac{\sigma_{\text{b,coh}}}{E} \sum_i^{\text{Bragg}} f_i e^{-4W(T)E_i^{\text{Bragg}}} \quad (3)$$

where $\sigma_{\text{b,inc}}$ and $\sigma_{\text{b,coh}}$ are the bound incoherent and coherent cross sections, respectively, and f_i is the form factor for the i^{th} lattice plane and is related to the crystalline structure and the lattice plane spacing. Thus, as temperature increases, thermal expansion in the crystal leads to an increase in the lattice plane spacing, which affects the form factor. This temperature dependence, however, is not supported in the ENDF-6 format and is thus typically neglected.

3. MLP GENERATION

The MLP generation performed in this work follows a similar procedure to that used in Ref. [8]. Training set calculations and MLP generation were performed in MedeA [12]. A $2 \times 2 \times 2$ supercell of MgO was constructed and simulated using AIMD for 1600 fs (timestep size of 4 fs) at three temperatures: 300 K, 1200 K, and 2500 K. For each temperature, every fourth frame was reanalyzed using a high-accuracy single-point DFT calculation and added to the training set. Across all three temperatures, the training set consisted of 300 structures. All DFT calculations in the present work were performed using VASP-6 [13, 14] and used the GGA-PBE exchange-correlation functional [15] with projector-augmented wave (PAW) potentials [16]. The MLP was then trained on the 300 structures in the training set, with an optimized radial cutoff of 4.73158 Å and optimized relative radii of 0.38010 and 0.48254 for Mg

and O, respectively. An energy comparison (Fig. 2A) across the structures in the training set verifies that the MLP accurately reproduces the cases for which it was trained, with a small maximum error < 0.004 eV/atom. The energies in this comparison plot form three clusters which correspond to the three temperatures included in the training set (300 K, 1200 K, and 2500 K).

While the comparison in Fig. 2A indicates that the MLP adequately represents the DFT force field, further validation is required. The MLP was used in MD calculations with the LAMMPS molecular dynamics code [17] to calculate the lattice parameter as a function of temperature. For these calculations, a $5 \times 5 \times 5$ supercell was simulated with an nPT thermostat for 100 ps with a 3 fs timestep. The ratio between the resultant lattice parameters and the corresponding room temperature lattice parameters are shown in Fig. 2B and compared to experimental measurements [18, 19, 20, 21, 22].

Figure 2. The error between the DFT-calculated energies and MLP-calculated energies of the training set are shown (A), along with a comparison of the MLP-calculated lattice expansion against experiment (B).

The reliability of the MLP for computing temperature-dependent phonon distributions is crucial in order to describe thermal neutron scattering events, as well as derived quantities such as the Debye-Waller coefficient. Initially, a study on the ground state phonon distribution is conducted, where MLP-calculated forces are input into the PHONON code [23] using the MedeA automation toolkit. These results are then compared with phonon distributions obtained from VASP-6 DFT calculations linked to the PHONON code. These DFT-generated phonon distributions were calculated both accounting for and neglecting the effect of LO/TO splitting. The LO/TO splitting accounts for the separation of longitudinal optical (LO) and transverse optical (TO) phonon modes due to long-range electrostatic interactions in polar materials. Phonon densities of states for each case are presented in Fig. 3. The MLP, which presently excludes polarization, accurately reproduces the corresponding DFT phonons without LO/TO splitting.

4. THERMAL SCATTERING LAW GENERATION

The MLP can be used to generate temperature-dependent phonon distributions for inelastic thermal neutron scattering profiles. Using LAMMPS, $20 \times 20 \times 20$ supercells of MgO were relaxed and simulated over 40,000 timesteps with a timestep size of approximately 0.00021 ps. Atomic velocities were recorded every two steps, then post-processed to construct the velocity auto-correlation function (VACF). The phonon distribution was obtained by performing a Fourier transform on the VACF and applying a smoothing filter to reduce numerical noise. The partial phonon distributions, Mg(MgO) and O(MgO), are shown in Fig. 4. As the material temperature increases, the phonon spectra exhibit noticeable softening with vibrational frequencies decreasing. Additionally, anharmonicity-driven broadening of phonon

Figure 3. Ground state phonon densities of states are provided, as calculated using the MLP and DFT (with and without LO/TO splitting enabled).

peaks increases with increasing temperatures, diminishing the phonon spectrum features and extending the maximum available phonon energy.

Figure 4. The partial phonon densities of states for Mg(MgO) and O(MgO) are shown above, as calculated using the MLP at a variety of temperatures. At low temperatures the spectra resemble those depicted in Fig. 3, however the distributions soften as temperature increases.

In order to generate the processed inelastic and elastic thermal scattering data, the phonon distributions, crystal structures, and other nuclear parameters are provided to the FLASSH [24] thermal scattering law evaluation code. In constructing the temperature-dependent cell structures, experimentally-determined lattice parameters are adopted as opposed to MLP-generated lattice parameters. The lattice parameters used in this work are determined by fitting a low-order polynomial to the experimental measurements [18, 20, 22]. Lattice parameters for each evaluation temperature are tabulated in Table I.

Table I. Experimental lattice parameters from averaging the results of [18, 20, 22].

Temperature [K]	293.6	400.0	600.0	800.0	1000.0	1200.0	1600.0
Exp. Lattice Parameter [Å]	4.21125	4.21586	4.22657	4.23868	4.25122	4.26388	4.29173

In order to highlight the effects of full temperature-dependence, two cases are considered: (1) a fully

temperature-dependent case, utilizing temperature-dependent MLP-generated phonon distributions (Fig. 4) and temperature-dependent experimentally-determined lattice parameters (Table I), and (2) a case where a single temperature-independent AILD-generated phonon distribution without LO/TO splitting (Fig 3) is used along with the 293.6 K experimentally-determined lattice parameter from Table I. These two cases are processed using FLASSH which, among other things, calculates elastic and inelastic thermal scattering cross sections. The processed inelastic and coherent elastic scattering cross sections are shown in Fig. 5A and Fig. 5B, respectively, for temperatures of 293.6 K, 600 K, and 1600 K.

The impact of the temperature-dependent MgO material model increases with increasing temperature for both inelastic and elastic scattering. The temperature-dependent MLP-generated phonons yield a greater inelastic cross section than the temperature-independent AILD for neutrons above 0.001 eV. However, above 600 K a bias in the $1/\sqrt{E}$ behavior is observed below 0.001 eV. Temperature-dependent lattice parameters cause a decrease in the Bragg energy within increasing temperature; although, this effect is more subdued at or below 600 K than at 1600 K. Temperature-dependent phonons have a substantial impact on elastic scattering, whereby the magnitude of Bragg peaks in the fully temperature-dependent case are biased below those computed with AILD methods (deployed in ENDF/B-VIII.1).

Figure 5. Thermal scattering cross section comparisons are provided for inelastic scattering (A) and coherent elastic scattering (B), where the temperature dependence of both phonon distributions and lattice parameters drive discrepancies between the MLP-generated results and the AILD-generated results.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We have demonstrated a TSL evaluation workflow that can be used to relax the temperature independent approximation that has historically been used for solid moderators. This study emphasizes the significance of incorporating temperature-dependent Bragg energies in thermal scattering law evaluations for coherent elastic neutron scattering. Using magnesium oxide (MgO) as the example material, the impact of thermal expansion on Bragg energies and coherent elastic scattering behavior was illustrated. Fully temperature-dependent models offer more accurate representations of scattering phenomena and may be enabled through the adoption of the Generalized Nuclear Data Structure (GNDS) [25]. This work highlights the benefits of a refined coherent elastic scattering physics model which, subject to data processing and format specifications, could be available in future ENDF/B-IX releases. Future work may explore the utilization of temperature-dependent Bragg edges in transport calculations, including appropriate temperature interpolation methods.

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